

Benchmarking and New Strategy for Monte Carlo Neutron Transport with Thermal-Hydraulic Feedback

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ABSTRACT

Rapid development of Monte Carlo transport methods and high-performance computing has enabled coupled Monte Carlo neutronics simulations with thermal-hydraulics coupling simulations to be widely researched and applied in reactor designs and analyses. Various coupling strategies have been developed to enhance the convergence stability and efficiency of the coupling iterations. In this work, a benchmark problem for coupled Monte Carlo neutron transport with thermal-hydraulics feedbacks is established, and an optimization problem is defined to examine the efficiency of the coupling iterations. Several existing coupling strategies including the traditional relaxation method, the Robbins-Monro method, and the asymptotic batch coupling method are introduced, and a new dynamic particle histories strategy is proposed based on the analysis of error accumulation in the general relaxation framework. Then, all these strategies are conducted and compared on the established benchmark problem. The results of the experiments demonstrate that the proposed growing number of neutron histories strategy outperforms other existing methods in terms of figure of merit and it is also insensitive to the method coefficients, which indicates its effectiveness in suppressing error propagation and accumulation and its feasibility in practical applications. Further studies and optimizations can be explored based on this strategy and benefit from the established benchmark problem.

Keywords: Monte Carlo, thermal-hydraulic feedback, benchmarking, comparison of coupling strategies

1. INTRODUCTION

Rapid development of Monte Carlo neutron transport methods and high-performance computing has enabled Monte Carlo (MC) neutronics and thermal-hydraulics (TH) coupling simulations to be widely researched and applied in reactor designs and analyses. Here the authors would like to study the efficiency of this coupling iterations and propose strategies to improve it.

As the TH feedback is typically negative for light water reactors (LWRs), and can be large enough to destabilize the iteration process [1, 2], various coupling methods have been developed to enhance the convergence stability and thus efficiency. Typically, a relaxation technique is often employed to suppress the oscillations caused by the strong TH feedback. However, a simple relaxation method may not be sufficient to stabilize the coupling iterations due to multiple factors, including the nonlinearity of the coupling equations, the presence of statistical noise in the MC simulations, etc. Therefore, more advanced methods have been proposed: Dufek and Gudowski [3] examined the Robbins-Monro algorithm [4] in the context of MC-TH coupling, where the relaxation coefficient is adjusted over iterations to enhance stability; Kelly et al. [5] increased the number of particle histories tracked in the later iterations to reduce unnecessary computing effort in the early unstable iterations; Gill et al. [6] suggested to reduce the number of source iterations between two TH calculations to converge quickly and stably; Li

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et al. [7, 8] also used fewer source iterations and proposed the asymptotic batch coupling method from theoretical analyses on the stability of the coupling iterations.

All of the aforementioned methods can be abstracted into the general relaxation framework of coupling iterations with different strategies for settings of method coefficients. To optimize these coefficients and thus design more efficient methods, it is essential to build a representative benchmark problem and analyze the convergence process of the coupling iterations, which is the main objective of this study.

In this work, the authors first introduce the definitions of the general relaxation framework and its changeable coefficients. Then, a simplified yet representative problem for the MC-TH coupling simulations on LWRs is established. This problem then serves as a testbed for evaluating the performance of various coupling strategies. The subsequent sections are organized as follows: Section 2 presents the definitions of the general relaxation framework and the optimization problem; Section 3 introduces several coupling strategies, including the proposed dynamic particle histories strategy; Section 4 conducts the comparison of these strategies on the established benchmark problem; Section 5 presents the conclusions and outlines potential future works.

2. PROBLEM DEFINITION

2.1. General Relaxation Framework of Coupling Iterations

The general relaxation framework for coupling iterations can be expressed as follows:

$$\mathbf{x}^{(k+1)} = \alpha^{(k+1)} \left[\mathcal{G}(\mathbf{x}^{(k)}) + \boldsymbol{\epsilon}^{(k+1)} \right] + (1 - \alpha^{(k+1)})\mathbf{x}^{(k)} \quad (1)$$

where $\mathbf{x}^{(k)}$ represents the solution vector at the k -th coupling iteration, \mathcal{G} denotes the coupling operator that encompasses both neutronics and thermal-hydraulics calculations. The operator \mathcal{G} is precise, and all the MC statistical errors, TH truncation errors, etc. are collected in $\boldsymbol{\epsilon}^{(k+1)}$ at the $(k+1)$ -th iteration. $\alpha^{(k+1)}$ is the relaxation coefficient that may vary over iterations.

Expanding Eq. (1) and then the contribution of the errors from all previous iterations to the current solution can be expressed as:

$$\boldsymbol{\epsilon}_k = \mathbf{x}^{(k)} - \mathbf{x}_*^{(k)} = \sum_{j=1}^k \left(\alpha^{(j)} \boldsymbol{\epsilon}_{\mathcal{G}}^{(j)} \right) + \sum_{j=1}^k \left(\alpha^{(j)} \left[\prod_{i=j+1}^k (1 - \alpha^{(i)}) \right] \boldsymbol{\epsilon}^{(j)} \right) + \left(\prod_{i=1}^k (1 - \alpha^{(i)}) \right) \boldsymbol{\epsilon}^{(0)} \quad (2)$$

where $\boldsymbol{\epsilon}_k$ is the total error at the k -th iteration, which is different from the error in each iteration $\boldsymbol{\epsilon}^{(k)}$. $\mathbf{x}_*^{(k)}$ is the exact solution at the k -th iteration without errors, and it can be obtained by recursively applying the coupling operator \mathcal{G} as:

$$\mathbf{x}_*^{(k+1)} = \alpha^{(k+1)} \mathcal{G}(\mathbf{x}_*^{(k)}) + (1 - \alpha^{(k+1)})\mathbf{x}_*^{(k)} \quad (3)$$

and

$$\boldsymbol{\epsilon}_{\mathcal{G}}^{(j)} = \mathcal{G}(\mathbf{x}_*^{(j-1)}) + \boldsymbol{\epsilon}_{j-1} - \mathcal{G}(\mathbf{x}_*^{(j-1)}) \quad (4)$$

is the error propagated through the coupling operator \mathcal{G} .

Typically, the initial guess of the solution $\mathbf{x}^{(0)}$ is deterministic, that is:

$$\boldsymbol{\epsilon}^{(0)} = 0 \quad (5)$$

and thus

$$\mathbf{x}^{(0)} = \mathbf{x}_*^{(0)} \quad (6)$$

Therefore, the last term of Eq. (2) can be eliminated. To simplify the description, the other two terms of Eq. (2) are marked as $\epsilon_{\mathcal{G},k}$ and $\epsilon_{cal,k}$, respectively.

Stability analyses of the coupling iterations in the previous works [1, 8] focused on the first term $\epsilon_{\mathcal{G},k}$, which represents the propagation and accumulation of errors through the coupling operator. When the spectrum radius of the operator \mathcal{G} is less than 1, the coupling iterations are stable in the absence of statistical errors. However, when statistical errors are present, even if the spectrum radius of \mathcal{G} is less than 1, the iterations may still become unstable. Therefore, the authors focus on the second term $\epsilon_{cal,k}$ in this study.

For simple relaxation settings with fixed coefficient $\alpha^{(k)} = \alpha$ and fixed number of particle histories, the term $\epsilon_{cal,k}$ can be simplified as:

$$\epsilon_{cal,k} = \alpha \sum_{j=1}^k (1 - \alpha)^{k-j} \epsilon^{(j)} \quad (7)$$

As $0 < \alpha < 1$, the weights of the errors from previous iterations decrease exponentially, but the errors from recent iterations may be largely retained. That is why optimization of the relaxation framework is essential to enhance the stability of the coupling iterations.

2.2. Coupling Benchmark and Optimization Problem

According to the previous studies [8] for MC and TH coupling simulations, the coupling system may become more unstable when the system size increases. Therefore, to establish a benchmark problem that can represent practical LWR simulations, an array of 15 assemblies shown in Fig. 1 is considered as the benchmark, which may represent typical commercial PWR core configurations of 121, 157, or 193 fuel assemblies. Each assembly is a standard commercial PWR 17x17 lattice assembly extracted from VERA Problem #6 [9].

Figure 1. Benchmark problem of 15 PWR 17x17 fuel assemblies arranged in an array

The side boundaries are set as reflective, and the top and bottom boundaries are vacuum. In that way, the model is super-critical, and the k_{eff} is around 1.36 without xenon. When xenon is manually added ($2.4 \times 10^{17} \text{cm}^{-3}$), the k eigenvalue is around 1.23. The number density of Xe-135 is estimated by burnup calculations.

The free parameters in the general relaxation framework on this benchmark problem include:

K : Total number of coupling iterations

$N_{act}^{(i)}$: Number of active source iterations for i -th coupling iteration

$N_{inact}^{(i)}$: Number of inactive source iterations for i -th coupling iteration

$P^{(i)}$: Number of neutron histories per cycle for i -th coupling iteration

$\alpha^{(i)}$: Relaxation coefficient for i -th coupling iteration

The optimization problem is then defined as finding the optimal set of these parameters to find the most precise solution with fixed computing resources. When the time cost of the TH calculations is negligible compared to the MC simulations, the total computing resources can be approximated as proportional to the total number of tracked particle histories:

$$C_{total} \propto P_{total} = \sum_{i=1}^K \left(N_{act}^{(i)} + N_{inact}^{(i)} \right) P^{(i)} \quad (8)$$

For the 15-assembly benchmark problem, C_{total} is set equivalent to tracking $P_{total} = 2 \times 10^9$ particle histories. The optimization objective is to minimize the error of the final solution $\mathbf{x}^{(K)}$ compared to the reference solution \mathbf{x}^* obtained with a very large number of particle histories and large number of coupling iterations.

3. COUPLING STRATEGIES AND EXPERIMENT SETUP

In this section, firstly several existing coupling strategies in the general relaxation framework are introduced. Then, a new strategy based on the analyses of the error term $\epsilon_{cal,k}$ in Eq. (7) is proposed. Finally, the experiment setup, parameter settings, and metrics for comparing these strategies on the established benchmark problem are provided.

3.1. Existing Coupling Strategies

3.1.1. Fixed alpha strategy

The traditional coupling method employs a fixed relaxation coefficient $\alpha^{(i)} = \alpha$ and fixed numbers of particle histories $P^{(i)}, N_{inact}^{(i)}, N_{act}^{(i)}$ over iterations. To classify from others, this method is denoted as “fixed alpha” in the following sections.

3.1.2. Robbins-Monro strategy

The relaxation coefficient $\alpha^{(i)}$ decreases over iterations according to the Robbins-Monro algorithm [4]:

$$\alpha^{(i)} = \frac{1}{i+1} \quad (9)$$

In this way, the weights of the errors from previous iterations are the same over iterations, which may better suppress the accumulation of errors.

$$\epsilon_{cal,k} = \sum_{j=1}^k \frac{1}{j+1} \prod_{i=j+1}^k \left(1 - \frac{1}{i+1} \right) \epsilon^{(j)} = \sum_{j=1}^k \frac{1}{k+1} \epsilon^{(j)} = \frac{1}{k+1} \sum_{j=1}^k \epsilon^{(j)} \quad (10)$$

This method is denoted as “Robbins-Monro” in the following sections.

3.1.3. Asymptotic batch coupling strategy

The asymptotic batch coupling strategy proposed by Li et al. [7, 8] is a coupling method with small numbers of source iterations between two TH calculations. In this way, the power distribution can asymptotically converge to the final solution. Also, more iterations of TH feedbacks may enhance the coupling between neutronics and thermal-hydraulics.

The specific numbers of inactive and active cycles in this strategy are determined according to the convergence and stability analysis. Typically, the numbers of active cycles are 20 to 30, and the number of inactive cycles should be sufficient for the first iteration (typically more than 100) and then can be neglected in the following iterations. The relaxation coefficient is fixed $\alpha^{(i)} = \alpha$.

This method is denoted as “asymptotic batch” in the following sections.

3.2. Growing Number of Neutron Histories Strategy

Let's define s_i as the total number of particle histories tracked in the i -th coupling iteration, and S_i as the total number of particle histories tracked in the first i iterations, i.e., $S_i = \sum_{j=1}^i s_j$. The proposed dynamic particle histories strategy aims to adjust s_i over iterations to suppress the accumulation of errors while keeping the relaxation coefficient $\alpha^{(i)}$ fixed.

Assuming that the statistical error $\epsilon^{(i)}$ in each iteration is inversely proportional to the m -th power of the number of particle histories s_i tracked in that iteration, i.e., $\epsilon^{(i)} \propto s_i^{-m}$, then a strategy can be designed to dynamically adjust the number of particle histories over iterations to suppress the accumulation of errors. Specifically, when only the MC statistical errors are considered, m should be 0.5 according to the central limit theorem, and thus $\epsilon^{(i)} \propto 1/\sqrt{s_i}$.

Given the total number of tracked particle histories P_{total} fixed according to Eq. (8), the number of particle histories can be allocated to minimize the error term $\epsilon_{cal,k}$ in Eq. (7):

$$\min_{\{s_i\}} \sum_{j=1}^k \alpha(1-\alpha)^{k-j} \frac{1}{s_j^m}, \quad \text{s.t.} \quad \sum_{i=1}^K s_i = P_{total} \quad (11)$$

Using the method of Lagrange multipliers, the optimal solution of Eq. (11) can be derived as:

$$\frac{s_{j+1}}{s_j} = \frac{1}{(1-\alpha)^{m+1}}, \quad j = 1, 2, \dots, K-1 \quad (12)$$

thus:

$$s_j = \left[1 - (1-\alpha)^{m+1}\right] S_j, \quad j = 2, \dots, K \quad (13)$$

Due to $s_j > 0$, $S_{j+1} > S_j$. Then according to Eq. (13), $s_{j+1} > s_j$. That is why this method is called “growing” number of neutron histories strategy.

To simplify the implementation, two variations of this strategy are used in the experiments:

- **G1:** $s_j = \alpha S_j$, which corresponds to $m = 0$ in Eq. (13), and can also be used as a rough approximation of the statistical errors with $m = 0.5$ and other uncertainties with $m < 0.5$;
- **G2:** $s_j = \alpha^2 S_j$, which is used to reduce the large differences between s_j values from the changing S1 strategy.

3.3. Experiment Setup

The experiments were conducted with the coupling system of the Monte Carlo neutron transport code RMC [10] and sub-channel thermal-hydraulics code SUBCHAN [11]. All the implementations of the coupling strategies discussed in Section 3.1 and 3.2 were integrated into this system.

Each coupling iteration involved a SUBCHAN thermal-hydraulics calculation based on the initial or obtained power distribution, followed by a RMC neutron transport simulation based on the updated temperature and moderator density distributions. The initial power distribution was assumed to be uniform in the horizontal direction and followed a cosine shape in the vertical direction of the 15-assembly benchmark problem.

The candidate parameters for different coupling strategies are provided in Table I. The values were selected to be similar across different strategies to ensure a fair comparison, but due to the inherent differences in the strategies, some variations were necessary.

method	fixed alpha	Robbins-Monro	asymptotic batch	G1	G2
K	8, 16, 32	8, 16, 32	16, 32	8, 16, 32	8, 16, 32
$N_{inact}^{(i)}$	100, 1	100, 1	set by algorithm	100, 1	100, 1
$N_{act}^{(i)}$	$1000 - N_{inact}^{(i)}$	$1000 - N_{inact}^{(i)}$	set by algorithm	$1000 - N_{inact}^{(i)}$	$1000 - N_{inact}^{(i)}$
$\alpha^{(i)}$	0.333, 0.666, 1.0	set by algorithm	0.5	0.1, 0.2, 0.3, 0.4	0.1, 0.2, 0.3, 0.4

Table I. Candidate parameters for different coupling strategies

The number of particle histories per cycle in each coupling iteration was determined based on the total number of particle histories $P_{total} = 2 \times 10^9$ and other parameters in Table I.

The performance of each coupling strategy was evaluated based on the convergence behavior of the power distributions, as well as the computational efficiency measured in terms of wall-clock time consumption. The figure of merit (FOM) was calculated to quantify the efficiency of each strategy:

$$\text{FOM} = \frac{1}{\sigma^2 t} \quad (14)$$

where σ is the norm of the power distribution error compared to the reference solution, and t is the total wall-clock time consumed for the simulation.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1. Comparison of the Results

The Final FOM factors for all the 72 cases with different methods or different coefficients are provided in Table II to V. To assist the comparison, the largest FOM for each method is boxed, and the second largest is underlined.

α	K	FOM	
		$N_{inact} = 1$	$N_{inact} = 100$
0.33	8	97.05	52.48
0.33	16	58.44	38.76
0.33	32	16.71	57.67
0.66	8	58.69	58.84
0.66	16	40.06	69.74
0.66	32	12.57	52.27
1.00	8	10.33	77.41
1.00	16	5.81	68.18
1.00	32	4.04	<u>83.66</u>

Table II. FOM factors of the fixed alpha method at the end of the simulations with different parameters

As shown in Table II to V, the asymptotic batch coupling method and the growing number of neutron histories strategy are the only two methods that can achieve a FOM factor higher than 100. This reveals that designing methods on the coupling stability analyses in [8] and the derived optimal allocation

α	K	FOM	
		$N_{inact} = 1$	$N_{inact} = 100$
set by algorithm	8	54.53	58.02
set by algorithm	16	<u>82.58</u>	55.52
set by algorithm	32	39.46	<u>58.95</u>

Table III. FOM factors of the Robbins-Monro method at the end of the simulations with different parameters

α	K	$N_{inact} + N_{act}$	FOM	
			$N_{inact} = 1$	$N_{inact} = 10$
0.5	16	60	6.65	<u>105.25</u>
0.5	32	30	5.13	<u>113.53</u>

Table IV. FOM factors of the asymptotic batch coupling method at the end of the simulations with different parameters

α	K	FOM of G1		FOM of G2	
		$N_{inact} = 1$	$N_{inact} = 100$	$N_{inact} = 1$	$N_{inact} = 100$
0.10	8	91.17	54.63	5.72	25.60
0.10	16	<u>115.72</u>	59.83	14.03	23.21
0.10	32	41.42	55.15	3.04	24.41
0.20	8	81.55	58.32	25.06	37.03
0.20	16	37.80	53.92	<u>110.85</u>	70.80
0.20	32	73.68	55.93	40.29	58.65
0.30	8	60.92	67.54	47.81	81.26
0.30	16	72.74	55.41	63.59	41.21
0.30	32	65.36	54.80	<u>116.69</u>	55.11
0.40	8	63.57	47.30	56.97	62.16
0.40	16	<u>104.43</u>	73.08	26.16	62.34
0.40	32	54.04	58.50	47.07	71.32

Table V. FOM factors of the growing number of neutron histories method at the end of the simulations with different parameters

strategy in Section 3.2 can effectively suppress the propagation and accumulation of errors and enhance the stability of the coupling iterations, which may lead to improved computational efficiency.

However, the FOM factors of the asymptotic batch coupling method is sensitive to its coefficients, and can be lower than 10 when the coefficients are not properly set. On the contrary, the G1 method yields similar FOM factors with different coefficients, indicating its robustness and feasibility in practical applications.

5. CONCLUSIONS

In this study, a benchmark problem for coupled Monte Carlo neutron transport with thermal-hydraulics feedbacks is established, and an optimization problem is defined to examine the efficiency of different coupling methods. The authors have introduced several existing coupling strategies and proposed a new growing number of neutron histories strategy based on the analysis of error accumulation in the

general relaxation framework. The results of the experiments demonstrate that the asymptotic batch coupling method and the proposed growing number of neutron histories strategy can effectively suppress error accumulation and accelerate the convergence of the coupling iterations. Furthermore, the proposed growing number of neutron histories strategy is insensitive to the selection of method parameters, making it feasible in practical applications. Future work may focus on further refining the growing number of neutron allocation strategy and exploring its applicability to more complex reactor geometries and coupling scenarios.

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